

Research Methodology
UAP Patterns and Indications 1945-1975
Intentions Study

Scientific Coalition for UAP Studies
Scientific Exploration of Anomalous Aerospace Phenomena

Research Methodology UAP Patterns and Indications 1945-1975 Intentions Study

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Abstract:

This paper presents the methodology used for a four-phase research project conducted by the Scientific Coalition for UAP Studies (SCU) Intentions Study team. The four phases of the project collected and analyzed data for Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena (UAP) in the United States associated with specific types of UAP activity observed during the period 1945-1975. The collection and analysis adhered to a curation standard, which included: 1) official report to military, law enforcement, or an entity that drafted a written report within one year, 2) report must contain sufficient detail to include the approximate date, time, location, and description of the encounter, 3) detail for the incident contained elements that were anomalous relating to structure, flight characteristics, and/or occupants associated with a UAP, 4) investigation must be conducted by an independent entity, to include efforts to establish eyewitness testimony, photographic/video evidence, instrumented data, and physical evidence, 5) Witnesses were military personnel, civilians employed by military organizations, government employees, aircraft pilots and civilians filing a report with law enforcement.

1. Introduction

The Intentions Study team conducted a four-phase research project to investigate the intentions of unknown intelligence suspected to be engaging several elements within the US population. The four phases of the project conducted the same cycle of data collection based on a curation standard, and data analysis based on a structured analytic technique pertinent to each phase of the study. Conclusions were drawn based on the resulting analysis of indicators for scenarios examined for each study. The four papers comprising the study are: 1) UAP Pattern Recognition Study 1945-1975 US Military Atomic Warfare Complex (Hancock et al 2023a), 2) UAP Indications Analysis 1945-1975 United States Atomic Warfare Complex (Hancock et al 2023b), 3) UAP Activity Pattern Study 1945-1975 Military and Public Activities (Hancock et al 2024), and 4) UAP Indications Analysis 1945-1975 Military and Public Activities (Hancock et al 2025).^{1;2;3;4}

The Intentions Study team developed a curation methodology to collect data that focused on the veracity of the incident as opposed to the source providing a report of the encounter. The Intentions Study examined case studies of UAP to determine which cases provided the most reliable data based on the reported elements of the encounter. The more data available to place the event in space and time coupled with the investigation conducted into the encounter further validated the veracity of the case

studies used in the patterns and indications analysis. The Intentions Study team then developed the SCU UAP Intentions Study database to assess those cases that meet the standard of integrity outlined in this paper. Books cited in previous studies were canvassed for reports that met the curation standard for data collection. The design of the curation process evolved as the need for data points shifted by the study undertaken. Figure 1 below depicts the research design that drove the patterns and intentions study collection and analytical process.

Figure 1. Research Process

The patterns and intentions study team conducted a qualitative analysis of UAP incidents captured in both official and unofficial records that were further investigated by other entities. The veracity of these cases was further supported if an outside entity conducted an inquiry into the encounter. The analytical model applied structured analytic techniques, specifically the scenarios and indicators method to identify and mitigate biases in data collection.

A curation standard was applied to each study to ensure data that met the standard was included for analysis and determination of conclusions. Curation included general criteria for the quality of data, as well as specific criteria related to the scope and characteristics for each study. A list of terms was identified for keyword searches that served as a qualifier for incidents involving characteristics under study.

2. Data Sources

The same sources were used for the Pattern Recognition (Hancock et al 2023a) and Indications Analysis for the U.S. Military Atomic Warfare Complex (Hancock et al 2023b), and UAP Activity Pattern Study (Hancock et al 2024) and Indications Analysis for the Military and Public Activities (Hancock et al 2025). The sources were the Sparks 2020 list (composed largely of Air Force Bluebook Project investigations and reports), and the National Investigations Committee on Aerial Phenomena (NICAP) chronologies were used as the primary data sources for this study, supplemented by

Intercontinental Ballistic Missile (ICBM) related incidents described in the books *Clear Intent* (Fawcett and Greenwood, 1984), and *Faded Giant* (Salas and Klotz, 2005), and reports from the general public investigated by Dr. J. Alan Hynek, Dr. James McDonald, and NICAP field investigators.^{5;6;7;8}

3. Intentions Study Database

The data consists of an Excel database, with tabs for:

- “Data” containing curated list of 1163 incidents
- “Field Descriptions” containing descriptions for entry fields
- “Facility Type Reference” containing Facility Type codes and descriptions for military facilities
- “Facility Type By Year” containing annual quantification of data by Facility
- “NICAP” containing data extracted from the NICAP website

The Data tab contained columns for the entry of the following criteria for each incident curated for the study:

- Reference numbers for selected sources
- Date information
- Geographic location
- Facility description
- Comments from selected sources
- Facility Coding
- Activity Coding
- Study phase inclusion

After compiling the incident data into an Excel database, manual reviews were conducted to screen for incident relevance and to remove duplicate entries. Following the manual review, a reconciled final set of incidents was compiled for analysis.

Incident data was coded for the purpose of generating pivot tables, charts, graphs and demonstrative maps. An analysis code was assigned to each facility within each phase of the study. Each incident that included characteristics for the respective phase was assigned the corresponding analysis code. The frequency, interval and location of incidents was evaluated for patterns of UAP activity. The tables, charts, graphs and maps provided a visual depiction for relationships between the frequency, type of activity, location of activity, and established activity patterns, to assist with the evaluation of intention. Data for all four inter-related studies are included in a common database of 1163 UAP reports, available at <https://zenodo.org/records/14647871>

Figure 2. Sample Data Table, Pivot Table, Chart and Map

4. Assessment Terms and Scoring Characterization

The Intelligence Community Directive (ICD) 203 outlines standards for properly expressing uncertainties associated with major analytic judgments. Degrees of likelihood for an event or development encompass a full spectrum from remote to nearly certain. Analysts' confidence in an assessment or judgment may be based on the logic and evidentiary base that underpin it, including the quantity and quality of source material, and their understanding of the topic. Assessments should identify indicators that would alter the levels of uncertainty for major analytic judgments (ODNI, 2015).⁹

Expressions of likelihood or probability have been adapted from ICD 203 to include the following sets of terms and scoring:

almost no chance	very unlikely	unlikely	roughly even chance	likely	very likely	almost certainly
remote	highly improbable	improbable	roughly even odds	probable	highly probable	nearly certain
01-05%	05-20%	20-45%	45-55%	55-80%	80-95%	95-99%
			No data			
-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3

The scores for each scenario are based on a detailed analysis of the content and credibility of the individual reports associated with each indicator. A structured debate was used to collectively decide on the likelihood of each intention scenario based on the combined data.

5. General Selection Criteria - UAP Intentions Study

The data collection objectives of the patterns and intentions study focused on identifying those reports that met the curation standard and provided necessary data points for all four studies. These objectives changed depending on the particular focus of each study phase within the overall project.

The following are general criteria for the curation standard that guided selection of incidents for inclusion in the data set for all four studies:

- 1) **Incident Report** - The case was officially reported as an unidentified flying object to a military element, law enforcement, other government personnel with the authority to interrogate the general public, or other entity that drafted a written report. The report and any related field investigation had to be initiated within one year of the observation.
- 2) **Data Quality** - The report must contain sufficient detail to include the approximate date, time, location, and description of the encounter.
- 3) **Anomalous Characterization** - Detail for the incident contained elements that were anomalous relating to structure, flight characteristics, and/or occupants associated with a UAP.
- 4) **Investigation** - Investigation must be conducted by an independent entity, to include efforts to establish eyewitness testimony, photographic/video evidence, instrumented data, and physical evidence.
- 5) **Credibility** – Witnesses were military personnel, civilians employed by military organizations, government employees, aircraft pilots and civilians filing a report with law enforcement.

Data collection and analysis were compiled in spreadsheets, charts, graphs, and presentations. The team conducted weekly meetings via Zoom to discuss data for inclusion and exclusion. After data collection, the team met to conduct analysis which led to the creation of four study papers and an Estimate of the Situation.

6. Specific Criteria - Study Phases

Curation included specific criteria related to the scope and characteristics for all four studies. Each study had a specific scope of geography or function, and a set of characteristics that served as indicators for scenarios developed based on the scope for the study. For the purposes of the UAP Intentions Study, incidents related to the “military” and “public” were separated into domains. The separate study of military and public domains allowed for the examination of intention as it related to defense capability and opportunities for exploitation of the US population.

6.1. Pattern Recognition Study – US Atomic Warfare Complex

The UAP Pattern Recognition Study provides a view of the pattern of reported UAP in the US associated with the military atomic weapons complex between 1945 and 1975.¹ A set of 590 comprehensively documented UAP reports from this period were collected from selected sources, including Project Blue Book. These were analyzed graphically for spatial and temporal differences between the number of incidents reported at sites within the atomic warfare complex, and control sites. Initial study site classes were: 1) radioactive materials production plants, 2) atomic weapons assembly facilities, and 3) atomic weapons stockpile sites. The study also compared additional atomic weapons

deployment sites vs: 4) additional non-atomic military sites, and 5) major American rocket/missile and aerospace test and development facilities. Control sites classes were 1) civilian population centers and 2) high-security, non-atomic weapons military bases.

In collecting UAP reports associated with a particular facility or base, it was necessary to establish guidelines for the association of UAP reports for each study location. UAP reports would be collected for each study location, considering both, geographic distance and security zone (radar and interceptor). With each UAP incident, multiple factors were balanced when determining if a UAP incident is associated with a particular site. The study sites were organized into five phases which were divided by types of facilities:

1. Radioactive materials production plants
2. Atomic weapons assembly facilities
3. Atomic weapons stockpile sites
4. Strategic weapons (megaton) deployment bases
5. Rocket, missile and aerospace testing and development facilities

Understanding the sites Association Zone which is made up of the:

- Size of the physical security zone
- Size of the radar detection zone
- Size of the air defense zone

Understanding the individual factors of the UAP incident that may impact the likelihood of it being associated with a site such as:

- Location of the observer relative to the site
- Direction of travel of the UAP relative to the site
- Speed of the UAP
- Duration of the sighting

Sites Association Zone

Figure 3. Association Zone

Where multiple sites are near each other, the overlapping of zones needs to be considered. Due to the uniqueness of each site and the individual factors of each incident, it is necessary to review each incident to ensure the likelihood of the incident being associated with a site. If an incident cannot be determined to be associated with a study site, it was not included in the study. As an example, within New Mexico several of the bases are close to each other and UAP incidents that are observed around the wider site area need to be considered as potentially associated with another site.

Figure 4. Examples of overlapping association zones

Control sites were selected to provide a reference for exploring anomalous patterns in UAP incident activity, comparing conventional military sites and population centers with atomic warfare complex sites. The goal in selecting military control locations was to identify bases which did not have atomic weapons deployed during the time associated with the earliest period of the study. Population centers were selected as controls based on location within the same regional geography as the study site, but at a distance so that its UAP reports would not be duplicates of the study site. Cities and towns with population sizes comparable to the study sites were prioritized to reduce disparities simply based on disproportionate population sizes between study sites and control sites.

6.2. UAP Indications Analysis – US Atomic Warfare Complex

The UAP Indications Analysis for the US Atomic Warfare Complex provides an assessment of indicators associated with UAP reports included in the SCU Pattern Recognition Study (Hancock et al., 2023a).² The Pattern Recognition study analyzed UAP incidents geographically proximal to US military installations between 1945 and 1975. A set of 590 comprehensively documented UAP reports from this period were collected from select sources, including Project Blue Book. Study sites included: 1) atomic materials production, 2) atomic weapons assembly, 3) atomic weapons stockpiles, 4) atomic weapons deployment, and 5) rocket/missile testing and development. Further study of the UAP activity

frequency, type and pattern indicated the need to assess possible intentions relating to information collection, obstruction of military activities, and aggressive engagement. An additional 284 incidents were examined based on relevant UAP activity, for a total of 874 incidents. A list of indicators was created and mapped to four major scenarios for assessment, including General Military Survey, Atomic Weapons Survey, Atomic Warfare Prevention and Military Aggression.

The Intentions Study team developed a model providing a visual representation of the selected data, analysis and conclusions for the study.

The outline of the pattern and intentions analysis process are as follows:

- Collect and build a database of the most credible incidents possible.
- Chart the incidents to reveal patterns within the data.
- Analyze patterns to identify activity indicators.
- Map activity indicators to scenarios of “intent”

Figure 5. Intentions Study Model – Military Domain

A matrix was created for the assessment of 31 activities identified from reports included in the Pattern Recognition study (Hancock 2023a).

		Data Quality	Pattern Support	General Military Survey	Atomic weapons survey	Atomic Warfare Prevention	Military Aggression
1a	UAP activity at all first-generation atomic weapons materials production facilities						
1b	UAP activity at all first-generation atomic weapons design and assembly facilities						
1c	Extended surveillance at all first-generation atomic weapons design and assembly facilities						
2a	UAP activities at national atomic weapons stockpiles						
2b	Extended surveillance at national atomic weapons stockpiles						
3a	UAP activities at thermonuclear weapons deployment sites						
3b	Extended surveillance at thermonuclear weapons deployment sites						
4a	UAP reports from ICBM sites						
4b	UAP low altitude aerial incursions at ICBM bases						
5a	UAP incidents associated with ICBM test launches (Canaveral/Vandenberg)						
5b	UAP incidents associated with rocket and missile tests (White Sands)						
6	UAP incidents associated with manned space launches						
7	UAP activity at commercial nuclear power plants						
8	UAP activities suggestive of radiation/isotope monitoring and particulate collections						
9	UAP activities suggestive of testing of physical security at atomic military bases (Exclude ICBM)						
10	UAP activities suggestive of testing air defenses at atomic development facilities						
11	UAP activities suggestive of testing of air defense capabilities at conventional military bases						
12	UAP activities suggestive of testing of physical security at conventional military facilities						

13	UAP activities at atomic weapons tests						
14	UAP low altitude aerial incursions at conventional military bases						
15a	UAP incidents associated with atomic bomber alert missions						
15b	UAP incidents associated with atomic bombing exercises						
15c	UAP activity associated with continental air defense exercises						
16	UAP activities associated with mobile atomic weapons platforms (submarines and aircraft carriers)						
17a	UAP encounters suggesting testing of aircraft capabilities (speed, response times, maneuverability)						
17b	UAP activity suggesting of false duplication of IFF (Identification Friend or Foe) radar responses to air defense radar facilities						
17c	UAP incidents suggestive of jamming or other types of electronic interference with military aircraft radar systems						
18	Detection and tracking capabilities reconnaissance (visual and radar)						
19	Clandestine UAP activity						
20	Overt UAP activity						
21	Direct engagement with military involving substantial risk or sustained damage, personal injury, or death						

Figure 6. Military Indications Analysis Matrix

Incidents that had sufficient detail, appropriate witness validation, and contained UAP activities in the matrix, met standards for inclusion in the data set.

6.3. Activity Pattern Study – Military and Public Activities

The UAP Activity Pattern Study for the Military and Public Activities reviews patterns of reported UAP in the US associated with nine specific types of UAP observed during the period 1945-1975.³ The activities included 1) interactive flight, 2) radical flight, 3) electronic transmissions, 4) interference with military weapons systems, 5) intrusions at military installations, 6) loitering, 7) close approaches, 8) observed occupants, and 9) encounters with occupants. Our previous studies for the same period focused on patterns (Hancock, et al, 2023a) and indications (Hancock, et al, 2023b) of UAP incidents reported to the U.S. military, particularly in the context of the development of the atomic warfare complex and the deployment of strategic atomic weapons. These studies analyzed activity based on location and association with military activities, which indicated an intelligent and focused survey of US atomic weapons development. While this study addresses a separate question to that of the previous studies, they use the same UAP report sources and there is an overlap of incidents between the three studies. A set of 505 UAP incidents were selected from Project Blue Book, the National Investigations Committee on Aerial Phenomena (NICAP), Clear Intent (Fawcett and Greenwood, 1984), and Faded

Giant (Salas and Klotz, 2005). The incidents were chosen after a comprehensive investigation to ensure sufficient information was available to characterize the activities and that the incident displayed at least one of the nine specific types of UAP activity being studied. Incidents that had sufficient detail, appropriate witness validation, and contained any of the nine identified UAP activities for study, met standards for inclusion in the data set.

6.4. UAP Indications Analysis Study - Military and Public Activities

This paper provides an assessment of indicators associated with UAP reports included in the SCU Activity Pattern Study. ⁴ The Activity Pattern Study and Indications Analysis for Military and Public Activities was conducted in association with the Pattern Recognition ([Hancock et al., 2023a](#)) and Indications Analysis for the US Atomic Warfare Complex ([Hancock et al., 2023b](#)). The Activity Pattern study analyzed UAP incidents in the military and public between 1945 and 1975. A set of 597 comprehensively documented UAP reports from this period were collected from select sources, including Project Blue Book. Seven UAP intention scenarios were evaluated in this work: 1) Survey - Human Behavioral Studies, 2) Recognition, 3) Contact, 4) Communication, 5) Collaboration, 6) Unilateral Assistance, and 7) Unilateral Exploitation. A list of indicators was created and mapped to the seven major scenarios for assessment.

The Intentions Study team developed a model providing a visual representation of the selected data, analysis and conclusions for the study.

Figure 7. Intentions Study Model – Military and Public Domain

A matrix was created for the assessment of 13 activities identified from reports included in the Activity Pattern study (Hancock 2024).

Indicators	Data Quality	Pattern Support	Human behavioral studies Our reaction to them	Contact Protocol			UI Unilateral	
				Recognition (UI)	Contact	Communicate	Collaboration	Assistance
Visibility (are they visible)								
Geographic distribution								
Interactive flight								
Radical flight								
Electronic transmissions (IFF)								
Interference with weapons systems								
Intrusions at military facilities								
Loitering								
Close approach								
Occupant observed								
Occupant encounter								
Aircraft encounters								
Engagement with aircraft								

Figure 8. Military and Public Indications Analysis Matrix

Incidents that had sufficient detail, appropriate witness validation, and contained UAP activities in the matrix, met standards for inclusion in the data set.

7. Conclusions

Using this methodology, the pattern analysis for UAP incidents was evaluated for the military and public domains to identify trends for visibility, daylight vs nighttime, UAP activities for interactive flight, radical maneuvers, loitering, electronic transmissions, military intrusions, and weapons system interference; and UAP occupant activities for close approaches, occupant observed and occupant encounters. Documented activity patterns were examined for changes and trends throughout the period of study.

A timeline with significant changes in UAP, as well as significant events for the development of warfare capabilities were used to track the interaction of UAP with the US atomic warfare complex. Elevations in activities that aligned with various stages of development were used as support or lack of support for association of UAP special interest.

Key points were identified for the analysis to assist with interpretations of patterns and trends for each activity. Elevations in frequency were noted for activities at locations based on association to general military assets, military assets involved in the production, assembly, deployment of atomic weapons, public areas designated as controls for military study sites, and public locations from which UAP reports were generated with qualified data and sources suitable for the study. The duration, in combination with frequency for activity elevations, were also noted as support or lack of support for patterns. Patterns in the data provided context for specified activities related to possible scenarios of

intent. Based on the frequency, type and patterns identified during the analysis, each scenario was profiled for likelihood of intention.

Scenarios for the US Atomic Warfare Complex were identified as:

- General Military Survey
- Atomic Weapons Survey
- Atomic Warfare Prevention
- Military Aggression

The survey-related scenarios narrowed the scope of examination for apparent presence of unknown intelligence at sensitive and restricted locations. Intelligence assessments use levels of activity to indicate special interest. Elevations of activity would indicate a special interest, which then point to the need for an assessment of the activity of interest. A lack of distinction in activity for general military assets vs military assets involved in the development of atomic weapons indicates no special interest, and therefore does not indicate an evaluation of any specialized function of the military. However, a special interest in atomic weapons development indicates counterintelligence activities.

Counterintelligence is the gathering of sensitive information which may be used for plans to disrupt operations. Efforts to disrupt military operations point to an advancement of engagement that, regardless of whether the intent is benevolent or exploitative, is a threat to security. The question of benevolence or exploitation is addressed by the scenarios of Atomic Warfare Prevention and Military Aggression.

Repeated activities to disrupt military operations, with corresponding offensive maneuvers or actions would be interpreted as aggressive, and serve as the basis to engage in warfare. However, in the absence of offensive maneuvers or actions, disruption of military operations alone only indicates a message to disengage from military warfare. The interpretation of this action is complicated due to the multiple layers of actions that may appear to represent benevolence. Benevolence is often used as a veil to gain advantage in a planned act of aggressive exploitation.

Scenarios for the Public and Military Activities were identified as:

- Survey - Human Behavioral studies
- Recognition of intelligence
- Contact
- Communications
- Collaboration
- Unilateral Assistance
- Unilateral Exploitation

An assessment of behavioral study, recognition, contact and communications scenarios involves a review of a generalized contact protocol. A general contact protocol establishes that the observer should act at a distance to gain attention and be recognized as foreign/unidentified. The observer should not make an immediate approach, and should maintain distance. The observer should minimize any action suggesting active threat or hostility and should take a slow approach, only if no target-of-interest flight is observed. The observer should leave immediately in response to either target-of-interest flight or fight reaction. The observer should limit any contact that may be interpreted as invasive or unclear. If “engaged” by a target-of-interest, the observer should not respond in any way and leave immediately without any covert or defensive action which might be interpreted as an aggressive response. The

observer should react to any target-of-interest response only passively, and no action should be taken that might suggest 'targeting'. The observer should approach only if given some passive signal of recognition, even if it is only a mimicking of the originating signal. There should be no proximity approach during initial contact. Approach should be strictly iterative, and non-threatening actions. Follow-on 'no threat' patterns of approach must be consistent and repetitive up to the point where mutual messaging is initiated.

The frequency, type and pattern of activities will inform the predominant mode of contact. The nature of contact and/or communications provide context for the establishment of a relationship. An established relationship sets an expectation for exchange as it relates to the resources. If there is no contact or communication and no exchange or acquisition of resources, the relative position of the observer (unknown intelligence) indicates a behavioral study. If the observer is recognized by the target-of-interest but there is no exchange or acquisition of resources, then recognition is the only identified point of interest with no other objective identified for the observer. If contact is made but no exchange or acquisition of resources, then contact is the only identified point of interest with no other objective identified for the observer. If communications are established, then a development may ensue regarding special interests which may serve as the basis for a relationship of mutual exchange, unsolicited assistance, or non-consensual removal of resources. The question of mutual exchange, unsolicited assistance, or non-consensual removal of resources is addressed by the scenarios of Collaboration, Unilateral Assistance and Unilateral Exploitation, respectively.

Based on the complexity of these factors, Intelligence Community Directive (ICD) 203 was used to establish levels of confidence for likelihood. Upon a determination of likelihood, each scenario was ranked.

Figure 9. Intentions Model - Combined Military and Public Domain

Methodology Constraints

Due to the parameters of the study period, future research is needed to determine whether patterns and trends emerged beyond the findings presented in these research studies. Due to limited data to establish patterns and trends for categories of activity, further study and request for data are required to enhance analysis and findings for areas of interest.

Credit Author Statement

L. J. Hancock: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. **I. M. Porritt:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization. **S. Grosvenor:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing., **L. Cates:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, **J. Pierson:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing

References

- ¹ Hancock, L. J., Porritt, I. M., Grosvenor, S., Cates, L., Okafor, I. (2023a). *UAP Pattern Recognition Study 1945-1975 US Military / Atomic Warfare Complex database*. Scientific Coalition for UAP Studies. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7295958>, Accessed 12 Feb 2024
- ² Hancock, L. J., Porritt, I. M., Grosvenor, S. (2023b). *UAP Indications Analysis 1945-1975 United States Atomic Warfare Complex*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7758498>, Accessed 12 Feb 2024
- ³ Hancock, L. J., Porritt, I. M., Grosvenor, S., Cates, L. (2024). *UAP Activity Pattern Study 1945-1975 Military and Public Encounters*. Scientific Coalition for UAP Studies. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8213330>
- ⁴ Hancock, L. J., Porritt, I. M., Grosvenor, S., Cates, L., Pierson, J. S. (2025). *UAP Indications Analysis 1945-1975 Military and Public Encounters*. Scientific Coalition for UAP Studies. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14647871>
- ⁵ Sparks 2020., (2020). Comprehensive Catalog of 2,200 Project Blue Book UFO Unknowns: Database Catalog, V1.30. NICAP. http://www.nicap.org/bb/BB_Unknowns.pdf, Accessed 2 Feb 2024
- ⁶ NICAP, UFO Chronology. <http://www.nicap.org/chronos>, Accessed 12 Feb 2024
- ⁷ Fawcett, L., B. Greenwood, (1984). *Clear Intent, The Government Coverup of the UFO Experience*, Prentice-Hall Inc., Pgs. 16-56, Pgs. 50-51, Pg. 53 ISBN: 978-0131366497
- ⁸ Salas, R., J. Klotz, (2005). *Faded Giant*, Burksurge LLC. Pgs. 12-27, Pgs. 4-11, ISBN: 978-1419603419
- ⁹ ODNI, “Analytic Standards,” Intelligence Community Directive 203 § (2015)